

Synthesis and characterization of uranyl $[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]$ complexes with benzothiazolyl hydrazones of benzil and diacetyl

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Abstract : A few uranyl complexes of the type $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{NO}_3]$ and $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$; where HL is a Schiff base obtained by the condensation of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole with benzil and diacetyl such as 2-(benzothiazolyl-2'-amino)imino-1,2-diphenylethanone (HBTDPPE) and 2-(benzothiazolyl-2'-amino)imino-1,2-dimethylethanone (HBTDMPE) have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, thermal analysis, infrared, electronic spectra and ^1H NMR studies. The results indicate that the former series of complexes of $[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]$ are six coordinated, while the later series of complexes are eight coordinated.

Keywords : Uranyl ion, benzil, diacetyl.

The dioxouranium(VI) ion is rather unusual in its structure and coordination behaviour. It has a linear shape¹ forming complexes with 4-8 donor atoms in the equatorial plane². In view of this unusual structure, coordination behaviour of dioxouranium(VI) ion, fluorescence characteristics and analytical applications of its complexes³, we report here synthesis and characterization of hitherto unknown uranyl complexes with some benzothiazolyl hydrazones such as HBTDPPE and HBTDMPE as shown below obtained by reaction of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole with benzil and diacetyl respectively.

X = C_6H_5 or CH_3

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

All the complexes are coloured, stable and non-hygroscopic. They decompose without melting above 200 °C. All are insoluble in water and most of the common organic solvents but slightly soluble in DMSO and DMF. Low molar conductance values in DMSO indicate they are non-electrolytes (Table 1). However the conductivity

value is higher than as expected for non-electrolytes probably due to partial solvolysis of the complexes in DMSO medium⁴. Uranium was estimated gravimetrically as U_3O_8 . C, H, N content were determined by microanalysis using MLW-CHN micro analyzer, where as sulphur content was estimated as BaSO_4 ⁵.

The elemental analytical data are in agreement with the stoichiometry of all the uranyl complexes.

IR spectra : The ligands reveal characteristics bands at ~ 3100 , ~ 2910 , ~ 1710 and ~ 1650 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ phenyl ring or methyl, $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ azomethine vibrations respectively. Apart from these bands, a multiple band system of medium intensity is observed at ~ 1600 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ cyclic, ~ 1540 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ cyclic and ~ 1360 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ cyclic which may be due to ring stretching vibration mode of benzothiazole moiety⁶. The bands occurring at ~ 1220 and ~ 1050 cm^{-1} may be due to the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ exocyclic stretching vibration and $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ stretching vibration respectively. Beside the above bands, a band of medium intensity appeared at ~ 750 cm^{-1} which may be due to $\nu_{\text{C-S-C}}$ benzothiazole ring vibration. The position of the band due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ cyclic, $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ cyclic remain practically unaltered in the present complexes indicating non-coordination of ring nitrogen atom to the uranyl ions, whereas the position of $\nu_{\text{C-S-C}}$ band shifted to lower frequency by 10-20 cm^{-1} in all the complexes indicating coordination of ring sulphur atom to the uranyl ion⁷. In the spectra of complexes the band due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ was found to be absent and two new bands of me-

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Compds.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		U	C	H	N	S	
[UO ₂ (BTDPE)(H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃)]	Cabinet grey	32.83 (32.87)	34.81 (34.85)	2.48 (2.52)	7.71 (7.73)	4.37 (4.41)	26.20
[UO ₂ (BTDME)(H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃)]	Canary yellow	39.63 (39.66)	22.00 (22.06)	2.33 (2.39)	9.30 (9.33)	5.29 (5.33)	23.66
[UO ₂ (BTDPE) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Chocolate	23.35 (23.37)	49.51 (49.58)	3.14 (3.19)	8.21 (8.25)	6.27 (6.28)	21.91
[UO ₂ (BTDME) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish brown	30.85 (30.90)	34.02 (34.08)	3.11 (3.18)	10.87 (10.90)	8.29 (8.31)	20.82

dium intensity at ~ 1580 and $\sim 1530 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ appeared instead which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ respectively indicating the ligands coordinated to the uranyl ions through deprotonation of enolic OH after enolisation via tautomerism^{8,9}. Consequently the bands due to azomethine $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ of the ligands were absent and a new band appeared at $\sim 1560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ indicating thereby coordination of one of the nitrogen atoms of the azo group to the uranyl ion. This is supported by the disappearance of the band at $\sim 3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{H}}$. All the complexes exhibits a strong band at $\sim 950\text{--}900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the medium intensity band at $\sim 830\text{--}820 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{as}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})}$ and $\nu_{\text{s}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})}$ mode respectively¹⁰. The coordination of nitrate ion in unidentate manner has been indicated by the appearance of additional band at the region ~ 1390 and $\sim 1050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the ν_2 and ν_4 modes of the vibration of coordinating nitrate ion under C_{2v} symmetry¹¹. Medium intensity bands at ~ 570 and $\sim 480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these complexes are assignable to M-O and M-N stretching vibra-

tion respectively. Besides, the bands observed at ~ 3400 and $\sim 880 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes might be assigned to $\nu_{\text{O}-\text{H}}$ and rocking mode of vibration of coordinated water which is further confirmed by thermal analysis.

Thermal analysis : The complexes are stable up to $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and thereafter a slight depression is observed up to $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This is due to loss of two coordinated water molecules¹² and takes place in a single step (Table 2). Simultaneous elimination of coordinated water molecules suggests them to be in the same chemical environment probably lying in the *trans* position perpendicular to linear uranyl moiety. Thereafter, the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents of the complex molecules as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues up to $\sim 650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and reaches to a stable product in each complex as indicated by the constant weight in the plateau of the thermogram. This corresponds to the composition of their stable oxide, U₃O₈.

The spectra of the ligands exhibits two strong bands

Table 2. Important features of thermo gravimetry analysis (TGA)

Compds.	Total wt. for TG (mg)	Temp. range of water loss ($^\circ\text{C}$)	% of water loss Found (Calcd.)	Temp. range of decomposition ($^\circ\text{C}$)	% loss of residue, U ₃ O ₈ Found (Calcd.)
[UO ₂ (BTDPE)(H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃)]	86	140-180	4.91 (4.97)	450-620	38.69 (38.76)
[UO ₂ (BTDME)(H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃)]	95	150-180	5.95 (6.00)	460-650	46.71 (46.77)
[UO ₂ (BTDPE) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	76	145-180	3.47 (3.53)	465-640	27.51 (27.56)
[UO ₂ (BTDME) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	82	148-180	4.62 (4.67)	470-650	36.37 (36.44)

in the region 210–230 and 300–375 nm, assignable to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ type and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ type transition respectively. The complexes display one weak band at 440 nm and a highly intense band in the range 280–290 nm, may be due to $1^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3^1\Pi_u$ transition and charge transfer transition respectively¹³. It may be noted that the band occurring at 370 nm due to uranyl moiety because of apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^o(U)$ transition¹⁴ is being merged with the ligand band due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition as evident from broadness and intensity.

The ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands and complexes are recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ (CDCl_3) medium. The ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand HBTDPPE shows a complex broad multiplet at δ 7.2–7.9 corresponding to 14 aromatic protons of the three phenyl groups and a singlet at $\sim\delta$ 8.9 due to proton of secondary amino group. On the other hand the ligand HBTDPME shows a complex broad multiplet in the region δ 7.2–7.9 corresponding four aromatic protons, a singlet at $\sim\delta$ 9.1 for one proton of secondary amino group and a twin peaks at $\sim\delta$ 2.8 and $\sim\delta$ 2.4 assignable to methyl protons for $-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ and $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ groups respectively¹⁵. The proton signal due to secondary amino hydrogen is absent in NMR spectrum of the uranyl complexes indicating the deprotonation of enolic $-\text{OH}$ via tautomerisation after complexation in conformity with the results of IR investigation, while the position of the other ^1H NMR peaks of the ligands remain practically unaltered. An additional peak at $\sim\delta$ 3.6 is observed in all the complex indicating presence of co-

ordinated water¹⁶.

From the results of the above studies, the following tentative structures have been assigned to 1 : 1 complex (Fig. 2) and 1 : 2 complex (Fig. 3) respectively.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The starting materials 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole was synthesized¹⁷ by refluxing the ethanolic solution of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole with hydrazine hydrate on water bath for about 3 h.

Synthesis of HBTDPPE : An ethanolic solution of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole was added to ethanolic solution of benzil (1 : 1 molar proportion) and the resulting solution was refluxed for about 4 h, cooled, when yellow coloured needle like crystals separated out. It was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol. The crystallized sample was dried in vacuo over fused calcium chloride and then analyzed (yield : 85%, m.p. 120 °C).

Synthesis of HBTDPME : It was prepared by similar method by refluxing 2-hydrazino benzothiazole with diacetyl in ethanol (yield : 82% m.p. 162 °C).

Preparation of complexes :

Complex of the type $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{NO}_3]$: Uranyl nitrate hexahydrate was dissolved in minimum volume of ethanol and added to a hot solution of ligand dissolved in the same solvent ($\text{M} : \text{L} :: 1 : 1$). pH was maintained at ~ 7 by dropwise addition of dilute NH_3 . The mixture was refluxed for 6–8 h on a water bath when a coloured complex was precipitated out in each case. It was filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried in vacuo over fused calcium chloride.

Complexes of the type $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$: These complexes were synthesized in the same manner as above by refluxing uranyl nitrate hexahydrate with appropriate ligand in the ethanol ($\text{M} : \text{L} :: 1 : 2$). The coloured complexes obtained in each case was filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried in vacuo over fused calcium chloride and analyzed.

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Fig. 2. Possible structure of 1 : 1 complex ($\text{X} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or CH_3).

Fig. 3. Possible that the structure of 1 : 2 complex ($\text{X} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or CH_3).

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